

BPM 2020 - Report

Cristina Cabanillas, Manuel Resinas, María Salas, Carlos Capitán, Adela del-Río-Ortega, Antonio Ruiz-Cortés

Universidad de Sevilla, Spain

1. Preprocessing of Participation Data

Before starting with the participation analysis, it should be pointed out that the participation data gathered from the congress has required a pre-processing stage, in order to be analyzed for this report.

First of all, it was necessary to reconstruct some strange connections. For instance, it was possible to find registers of a session that indicated that one participant connected from 10.00h to 10.30h, and later he or she connected from 10.20h to 10.35h. Thus there were duplicate registers, when there should be only one from 10.00h to 10.35h, these erroneous connections might have happened owing to the usage of different devices to connect to the same session or some connection errors. Also, some continuous connections are represented by different registers. For instance one register from 10.00h to 10.30h by one participant and later other register from 10.30h to 11.00h. In this case, both registers should be joined in one connection from 10.00h to 11.00h.

Secondly, the schedules of the sessions were estimated from the participation data, due to the connection data from some sessions could vary from the planned schedule, which could create problems to calculate their duration in the following analysis. The start times were approximated after detecting several join connections (20 connections) in a short space of time (60 seconds). Some sessions did not accomplish the first condition, therefore the connection threshold was reduced in these cases. Moreover, the ending times were approximated as the last leave connection. If we subtract the ending time minus the starting time, it obtains the duration of the session.

After that, we have filtered the participation data of each session depending on whether the sum of percentages of the attended time of a participant is bigger than a threshold. To estimate the percentages of attended time

we have calculated first the differences between the leaves time and the joins time of the connections. For example, if a participant connects from 10.25h to 10.35h and later this participant connects from 10.45h to 10.55h to a session, we consider that this participant attends 20 minutes. Taking into account this attended time, we have calculated his percentage by dividing this sum between the duration of a session. Continuing the previous example, if the session lasts 60 minutes, the attended percentage of this participant is 33%.

To find the threshold that states the attendance or not to a session, we have represented the average attendance percentage of all participants in a histogram with intervals from 5 to 5 (cf. Figure 1):

Figure 1: Histogram of average participation attendance

In this histogram, we have observed that between 5-10 and 10-15 there is a valley in the lowest percentages, which could indicate a change in the tendency, therefore it could be a good idea to set the threshold there. For instance, the attendance threshold could be set in 9%. The filter based on this threshold implies that if a session lasts 100 minutes and two participants have these attendances:

- Participant 1: 1 (1/100), 10 (10/100), and 15 (15/100): 26%
- Participant 2: 1 (1/100), 1 (1/100), and 5 (5/100): 7%

It would be considered that the second participant has not attended, since his summation of attended percentage is not bigger than the threshold,

but the attendance percentage of the first participant exceeds the threshold, therefore it would be considered that this participants attends.

Finally we have estimated the background of the participants to classify them in two groups, industrial and academic, depending on their emails and occupation.

2. Analysis of Participation per Session

In this section, we are going to analyse participation in congress per sessions. Therefore, we will obtain results directly related to the sessions. For example, which sessions have had the most participation or in which sessions the participants have stayed connected the longest. Also, the relationship between sessions according to participation will be analysed.

First, we have analysed the total number of participants that have been in each session of the congress with at least 9% participation in the session.

The total number of different participants in the congress is 912, after applying the attendance filter. Table 1 shows the number of participants in each session.

Sessions	Participants
Conference opening and Keynote - Perspectives in Process Mining - Closing the Big Data Gap	276
Keynote - Towards Process Science - Embracing Interdisciplinary Research Opportunities in the Digital Age	256
Awards and Conference closing	184
Morning Session	157
Keynote - How to infuse AI into Business Processes - A practitioner's perspective on best practices	156
Afternoon Session	143
Research Track Session 1 - Process Modeling and Conformance Checking (Triana Bridge)	130
Research Track Session 4 - Modeling Support and Maintainability (Cathedral)	129
Presentation of Industry Forum and Demo Teasers	124
BPM Forum Session 2 - Process Mining	114

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Sessions	Participants
Panel 1 - Publishing Culture in the BPM Community - Papers, papers, papers	109
Research Track Session 5 - Robotic Process Automation and BPM Maturity (Sierpes street)	100
Predictive Process Monitoring - From Theory to Practice	100
Research Track Session 2 - Social Context in BPM (Alcazar)	99
BPM Forum Session 1 - Prediction	99
Research Track Session 3 - Conformance and Prediction (Park)	99
Panel 2 - Privacy in Data-Driven Process Analysis - More Chance or Risk for Industry Adoption	95
Research Track Session 7 - Event data extraction, enhancement, and analysis (Setas)	95
RPA Forum Opening and Keynote - Robotic Process Automation for Process Transformation - Contemporary Themes and Research Challenges	90
Research Track Session 6 - Applications and organizational aspects of BPM (Alcazar Gardens)	89
Business Process Analysis using Scripting Languages	89
Workshop BPI'20	76
Joint Workshop BpMinDIT-2020 & BPM-Meet-IoT	73
BPM Forum Session 4 - Modeling	70
RPA Forum Demo Session	67
Demos and Resources (Room 1)	67
RPA Forum Session 1	64
Blockchain Forum	64
Information Systems Modeling - playing with the interplay between data and processes	62
BPM Forum Session 3 - Process Change, Maturity, and Culture	59
Demos and Resources (Room 3)	59
Demos and Resources (Room 2)	58
RPA Forum Session 2	55

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Sessions	Participants
Queue Mining - Process Mining Meets Queueing Theory	52
Driving Digitalization on the Shopfloor Through Flexible Process Technology	50
Industry Forum Session 1	49
Doctoral Consortium - Welcome and presentations by the PhD students	42
Blockchain Forum Keynote	37
Workshop DEC2H 2020	36
Industry Forum Session 2	33
Doctoral Consortium - Discussion and closure	29
Workshop SPBP'20	28
Workshop BPMS2'20	28
Demos and Resources (Room 5)	24
Demos and Resources (Room 4)	21

Table 1: Number of participants per session

As we can see in Table 1, the session with the largest number of different participants was *Conference opening and Keynote - Perspectives in Process Mining - Closing the Big Data Gap* with a total of 276 participants, followed by *Keynote - Towards Process Science - Embracing Interdisciplinary Research Opportunities in the Digital Age* with 256 participants and third-place *Awards and Conference closing with 184 participants*.

On the other hand, the sessions with the least participation were *Doctoral Consortium and Demos and Resources (Room 4)* with 21 participants, *Demos and Resources (Room 5)* with 24, and *Workshop BPMS2'20* with 28 participants.

Once the total number of participants per session has been analysed, we will analyse the number of simultaneous participants (connected at the same time) who have been in each session. For this, the average and the maximum number of simultaneous participants have been calculated.

Sessions	Mean	Max
Conference opening and Keynote - Perspectives in Process Mining - Closing the Big Data Gap	203.0	229.0
Keynote - Towards Process Science - Embracing Interdisciplinary Research Opportunities in the Digital Age	197.0	223.0
Awards and Conference closing	134.0	161.0
Keynote - How to infuse AI into Business Processes - A practitioner's perspective on best practices	114.0	133.0
Presentation of Industry Forum and Demo Teasers	92.0	106.0
Research Track Session 1 - Process Modeling and Conformance Checking (Triana Bridge)	88.0	104.0
Research Track Session 4 - Modeling Support and Maintainability (Cathedral)	87.0	105.0
Panel 1 - Publishing Culture in the BPM Community - Papers, papers, papers	82.0	98.0
Morning Session	77.0	102.0
Panel 2 - Privacy in Data-Driven Process Analysis - More Chance or Risk for Industry Adoption.	74.0	86.0
Afternoon Session	73.0	104.0
Research Track Session 5 - Robotic Process Automation and BPM Maturity (Sierpes street)	71.0	83.0
Predictive Process Monitoring - From Theory to Practice	68.0	83.0
Research Track Session 7 - Event data extraction, enhancement, and analysis (Setas)	66.0	77.0
BPM Forum Session 2 - Process Mining	66.0	77.0
BPM Forum Session 1 - Prediction	66.0	76.0
Business Process Analysis using Scripting Languages	64.0	72.0
RPA Forum Opening and Keynote - Robotic Process Transformation - Contemporary Themes and Research Challenges	64.0	70.0
Research Track Session 2 - Social Context in BPM (Alcazar)	63.0	76.0
Research Track Session 3 - Conformance and Prediction (Park)	62.0	74.0

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Sessions	Mean	Max
Research Track Session 6 - Applications and organizational aspects of BPM (Alcazar Gardens)	56.0	65.0
BPM Forum Session 4 - Modeling	49.0	60.0
RPA Forum Demo Session	44.0	54.0
RPA Forum Session 1	41.0	53.0
Joint Workshop BMinDIT-2020 & BPM-Meet-IoT	41.0	51.0
BPM Forum Session 3 - Process Change, Maturity, and Culture	41.0	55.0
Queue Mining - Process Mining Meets Queueing Theory	40.0	47.0
Blockchain Forum	40.0	46.0
Workshop BPI'20	39.0	49.0
Driving Digitalization on the Shopfloor Through Flexible Process Technology	37.0	47.0
RPA Forum Session 2	36.0	46.0
Information Systems Modeling - playing with the interplay between data and processes	35.0	44.0
Industry Forum Session 1	32.0	38.0
Doctoral Consortium - Welcome and presentations by the PhD students	27.0	34.0
Demos and Resources (Room 1)	25.0	35.0
Blockchain Forum Keynote	24.0	30.0
Demos and Resources (Room 2)	24.0	36.0
Industry Forum Session 2	22.0	26.0
Demos and Resources (Room 3)	21.0	33.0
Doctoral Consortium - Discussion and closure	21.0	27.0
Workshop DEC2H 2020	21.0	30.0
Workshop BPMS2'20	16.0	23.0
Workshop SPBP'20	15.0	25.0
Demos and Resources (Room 5)	9.0	14.0
Demos and Resources (Room 4)	8.0	13.0

Table 2: Simultaneous participants per session

Conference opening and Keynote - Perspectives in Pro-cess Mining - Closing the Big Data Gap, Keynote - Towards Process Science - Embracing Inter-

disciplinary Research Opportunities in the Digital Age, and *Awards and Conference closing* are the sessions that have had the greatest average number of simultaneous participants. Also, these three are the sessions that have had greater participation, as we have seen previously in Table 1.

Furthermore, for each of the sessions, we have analysed the evolution of the number of participants who have been connecting and disconnecting from the sessions. The graphs showing the evolution of simultaneous participants attending the sessions have been included in Appendix A.

Another important aspect that we have analysed is the average time that participants spend in the sessions, to study in which sessions they have spent the longest time attending. The results are shown in the following table, ordered descending according to the percentage of average attendance time.

Sessions	%Average attendance time
Awards and Conference closing	81.84
Presentation of Industry Forum and Demo Teasers	81.52
Panel 2 - Privacy in Data-Driven Process Analysis - More Chance or Risk for Industry Adoption	80.75
Doctoral Consortium - Discussion and closure	79.96
Queue Mining - Process Mining Meets Queueing Theory	79.42
RPA Forum Opening and Keynote - Robotic Process Automation for Process Transformation - Contemporary Themes and Research Challenges	78.45
Panel 1 - Publishing Culture in the BPM Community - Papers, papers, papers	78.31
Keynote - Towards Process Science - Embracing Interdisciplinary Research Opportunities in the Digital Age	77.10
Research Track Session 5 - Robotic Process Automation and BPM Maturity (Sierpes street)	77.07
Business Process Analysis using Scripting Languages	77.05
Driving Digitalization on the Shopfloor Through Flexible Process Technology	75.70

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Sessions	%Average attendance time
Research Track Session 1 - Process Modeling and Conformance Checking (Triana Bridge)	75.56
Industry Forum Session 2	74.02
Conference opening and Keynote - Perspectives in Process Mining - Closing the Big Data Gap	73.76
Keynote - How to infuse AI into Business Processes - A practitioner's perspective on best practices	73.42
Research Track Session 7 - Event data extraction, enhancement, and analysis (Setas)	72.57
BPM Forum Session 4 - Modeling	72.55
BPM Forum Session 3 - Process Change, Maturity, and Culture	72.11
Predictive Process Monitoring - From Theory to Practice	71.75
Industry Forum Session 1	70.25
BPM Forum Session 1 - Prediction	68.88
RPA Forum Session 2	68.29
BPM Forum Session 2 - Process Mining	68.04
RPA Forum Session 1	67.81
Research Track Session 3 - Conformance and Prediction (Park)	67.76
Research Track Session 4 - Modeling Support and Maintainability (Cathedral)	66.63
Research Track Session 2 - Social Context in BPM (Alcazar)	66.58
Blockchain Forum	66.42
Research Track Session 6 - Applications and organizational aspects of BPM (Alcazar Gardens)	66.04
RPA Forum Demo Session	65.91
Doctoral Consortium - Welcome and presentations by the PhD students	65.16
Blockchain Forum Keynote	63.77
Information Systems Modeling - playing with the interplay between data and processes	60.38

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Sessions	%Average attendance time
Joint Workshop BMinDIT-2020 & BPM-Meet-IoT	56.69
Workshop DEC2H 2020	56.67
Workshop BPMS2'20	54.51
Workshop SPBP'20	51.99
Afternoon Session	51.66
Workshop BPI'20	51.44
Morning Session	50.24
Demos and Resources (Room 4)	48.51
Demos and Resources (Room 5)	47.45
Demos and Resources (Room 1)	46.34
Demos and Resources (Room 2)	45.93
Demos and Resources (Room 3)	36.96

Table 3: Percentage of average attendance time

The best result has been obtained for the *Awards session and the closing* of the conference with 81.84%. The next two sessions with the highest percentage of average attendance time are the *Industry Forum Presentation and Demo Teasers sessions* and *Panel 2 - Privacy in data-based process analysis - More opportunity or risk for the adoption of industry*.

The following scatter diagram shows the relationship between the duration of the sessions and the percentage of average attendance time in the sessions.

Observing Figure 2, we can see a trend that shows how the percentage of average attendance time decreases as the duration of the session increases. The maximum value of the percentage of time is reached with a session with a short duration, while the minimum is obtained for a session of 2 hours approximately.

The 45 sessions of the congress can be classified into 8 groups according to their theme. The groups are *BPM, Blockchain, Industry, Modeling, Prediction, Process Mining, RPA* and *Others*. We have analysed the participation in the congress according to this classification.

To obtain the percentage of participation in each theme, we have calcu-

Figure 2: Scatter plot of the percentage of average attendance time spent in the sessions concerning their duration

lated the average of the participation percentages of all the sessions of the topic group.

The three themes with the highest percentage of participation are Process Mining, BPM, and Prediction. Process Mining sessions have been the most attended, with an average participation percentage of 15-16%. Meanwhile, Industry and Blockchain sessions have had fewer participants overall (Figure 3).

Moreover, we have analysed the percentage of average attendance time in each thematic group. In the Figure 4, we can see that the themes Process Mining, Industry, BPM, and RPA have the best results, reaching between 70% and 75% of average time assisted (Figure 4).

Finally, in this section, we have used clustering to group the sessions according to the common participants between them. Thus, to carry out this analysis we have omitted the sessions that did not take place with others in parallel, so they had a greater number of participants and influence the results. The deleted sessions are the follows:

- * Keynote - How to infuse AI into Business Processes - A practitioner's perspective on best practices
- * Keynote - Towards Process Science - Embracing Interdisciplinary Re-

Figure 3: Scatter plot of the percentage of participation in the sessions concerning their duration

search Opportunities in the Digital Age

- * Presentation of Industry Forum and Demo Teasers
- * Conference opening and Keynote - Perspectives in Process Mining - Closing the Big Data Gap
- * Awards and Conference closing

Figure 4: Scatter plot of the percentage of average attendance time spent in the sessions concerning their duration

- * Panel 1 - Publishing Culture in the BPM Community - Papers, papers, papers
- * Panel 2 - Privacy in Data-Driven Process Analysis - More Chance or Risk for Industry Adoption
- * Doctoral Consortium - Discussion and closure
- * Doctoral Consortium - Welcome and presentations by the PhD students

So, we have used the average percentage of common participants between pair of sessions. We explain it with the following example:

- Common participants between session 1 and 2: 25 participants
- Session 1: 75 participants
 - We calculate the percentage of participants in session 1 that is common to session 2, for this: $(25/75)*100 = 33.3\%$
- Session 2: 50 participants
 - We calculate the percentage of participants in session 2 that is common to session 1, for this: $(25/50)*100 = 50\%$
- The average percentage of common participants between session 1 and 2: $(33.3\%+50\%)/2 = 41.5\%$

We have made this calculation for all possible pairs of sessions, and we have related each session to the one with the highest percentage of common participants. Thus, we have represented in the following graph (Figure 5) the maximum similarity relationship between sessions.

In turn, the graph algorithm that we have used performs clustering on the graph itself. As a result, we have obtained 9 clusters differentiated by colors (Figure 5).

A graph is formed by a set of nodes (in this case the sessions) joined by links called edges, which allow representing associations between elements of a set. Therefore, the graph is made up of 44 nodes, due to fact that there are 44 sessions in the congress, and the edges between them have been created according to the average percentage of common participants.

In the previous figure, it can be appreciated that there are 9 clusters formed by different sessions.

The pink cluster is made up of all five RPA sessions, indicating that there is a relationship between them. Also, a session about Industry is included in this cluster.

On the other hand, the Process mining and Prediction sessions are jointly distributed among the water green, blue and orange clusters, so we can affirm that there is a relation between both themes.

The purple and lemon green clusters both contain Modeling and BPM sessions, along with others. Thus, we can also affirm that there is a relationship between both themes considering there is a high percentage of common users between them.

Figure 5: Session grouping graph using clustering

Regarding the two Blockchain sessions, these are grouped together in the green cluster.

3. Analysis of Participation per Person

In this section, we have studied aspects related to the attendance of the participants. We analysed first the hours which the users connected to the sessions. To do that, we represented the hour of the first connection of each user to each session in this histogram sorted by day (figure 6):

Figure 6: Histogram with the join hours sorted by days

Here it observes that the attendance peak is between 10:00h and 11:00h, with the exception of Sunday, Tuesday and Friday. All this data can be resumed in another global histogram that includes everyday (figure 7):

Where it can be appreciated more clearly that the peak is between 10:00h and 11:00h. Afterwards, we analysed the number of attended sessions by the participants, representing them in a histogram (figure 8):

Where we can observe that the majority part of the participants has attended between one and five sessions. Alternatively, it could be interesting to represent the total time spent in the congress by the participants (figure 9):

Clearly, the biggest part of the participants spent more than three hours, even though a minority spent more than ten hours. We considered that it would be interesting to study the correlation between the total time and the number of attended sessions, so we represented a scatter plot of both aspects (figure 10):

In figure 10, it can be noticed that the attendance to many sessions, it usually implies spending more time in the congress, even though there are

Figure 7: Histogram with all the join hours combined

Figure 8: Histogram of attended sessions by the participants

some cases which do not accomplish this tendency, because these participants might have attended less sessions but they attended the maximum time of them. Furthermore, we have studied the proportion of participants whose background is either academic or industrial (figure 11).

Although some participants are not represented due to his background is unknown, it is observable that there is an imbalance in the roles of the participants in figure 11. In addition, we have studied the number of attended sessions (NS), the average attended percentage (AAP) and total time in the

Figure 9: Histogram of the number of hours spent in the congress by participants

Figure 10: Scatter plot of total time spent in the congress with the number of attended sessions

congress (TT) of each group, to find differences (tables 4 and 5):

Statistic	NS	AAP	TT
mean	4.53	60.28	4.13
standard deviation	4.66	24.54	4.66
minimum	1.00	9.50	0.24
Q1	1.00	43.25	1.22

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Statistic	NS	AAP	TT
Q2	3.00	58.17	2.34
Q3	6.00	77.32	4.97
maximum	23.00	100.00	22.96

Table 4: Statistics about industrial participants

Statistic	NS	AAP	TT
mean	5.54	66.80	5.39
standard deviation	5.43	23.42	5.39
minimum	1.00	10.09	0.14
Q1	1.00	52.91	1.32
Q2	3.00	69.01	3.15
Q3	8.00	83.49	7.83
maximum	28.00	100.00	25.46

Table 5: Statistics about academic participants

In the previous tables it can be appreciated that the academic participants have spent more time in the sessions, and therefore they have dedicated more time to the congress, in comparison with the industrial participants. It is also important to highlight that there is a clear difference in the average attended percentage in both groups, since their standard deviations are high.

Since this data does not distinguish these groups, we have tried to find the sessions that can differentiate participants from the industrial and academic background, using the Fisher exact test with the binary attendance to sessions for both type of participants [1]. This test checks if two categorical variables with two possible values are related or not, using contingency tables. To check this possible relationship the test establishes two hypothesis (being alpha the threshold that determines the significance of the results):

- Null hypothesis (pvalue > alpha): the variables are independent, therefore there is no relationship.
- Rejection of null hypothesis (pvalue < alpha): the variables are depen-

Figure 11: Bar plot about the background proportions

dent, therefore there is a relationship between them.

In our case, these two variables are the background of the participants (academic or industrial) and the attendance to a session (yes or no), it must be highlighted that the attendance percentage must be at least 9%, to consider that the participant has attended and vice versa. Thus, if the pvalue is less than alpha, the background of the participants and the attendance to that session are related. These are the sessions whose pvalue is less than 0.5 in the test (table 6):

Session	Pvalue
Panel 1 - Publishing Culture in the BPM Community - Papers, papers, papers	0.000088
AI4BPM - Afternoon Session	0.000245
Awards and Conference closing	0.002288
Keynote - Towards Process Science - Embracing Interdisciplinary Research Opportunities in the Digital Age	0.003931
Research Track Session 1 - Process Modeling and Conformance Checking (Triana Bridge)	0.005949
Research Track Session 7 - Event data extraction, enhancement, and analysis (Setas)	0.006036

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Session	Pvalue
Blockchain Forum	0.008923
Panel 2 - Privacy in Data-Driven Process Analysis - More Chance or Risk for Industry Adoption	0.012171
Research Track Session 4 - Modeling Support and Maintainability (Cathedral)	0.016997
Predictive Process Monitoring - From Theory to Practice	0.023119
Queue Mining - Process Mining Meets Queueing Theory	0.033582
Research Track Session 2 - Social Context in BPM (Alcazar)	0.047683

Table 6: Most differential sessions

Consequently, these sessions (artificial intelligence, paper publishing, and the award session) distinguish these classes. On the other hand, we have studied the most attended and the least attended sessions of each group using the binary attendance data. For instance, in this table we have represented the sessions with the most binary attendance percentage (BAP) by industrial participants (table 7):

Session	BAP
Conference opening and Keynote - Perspectives in Process Mining - Closing the Big Data Gap	34.228188
AI4BPM - Afternoon Session	29.530201
AI4BPM - Morning Session	26.845638
Keynote - Towards Process Science - Embracing Interdisciplinary Research Opportunities in the Digital Age	20.805369
Keynote - How to infuse AI into Business Processes - A practitioner's perspective on best practices	20.805369
BPM Forum Session 2 - Process Mining	18.791946
Presentation of Industry Forum and Demo Teasers	17.449664
Awards and Conference closing	16.107383

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Session	BAP
RPA Forum Opening and Keynote - Robotic Process Automation for Process Transformation - Contemporary Themes and Research Challenges	13.422819
BPM Forum Session 1 - Prediction	12.080537

Table 7: Most attended sessions by industrial participants

Clearly, the sessions of artificial intelligence and forums were markedly attended. On the contrary, these are the least attended sessions by industrial participants (table 8):

Session	BAP
Demos and Resources (Room 4)	0.000000
Queue Mining - Process Mining Meets Queueing Theory	2.684564
Demos and Resources (Room 5)	3.355705
Workshop SPBP'20	4.026846
Doctoral Consortium - Discussion and closure	4.026846
Blockchain Forum	4.026846
Doctoral Consortium - Welcome and presentations by the PhD students	4.026846
Workshop DEC2H 2020	4.697987
Panel 1 - Publishing Culture in the BPM Community - Papers, papers, papers	5.369128
Industry Forum Session 2	5.369128

Table 8: Least attended sessions by industrial participants

In the previous table, it can be observed that industrial participants were not interested generally neither workshops nor demos. Furthermore, these are the most attended sessions by academic participants (table 9):

Session	BAP
Conference opening and Keynote - Perspectives in Process Mining - Closing the Big Data Gap	38.340807
Keynote - Towards Process Science - Embracing Interdisciplinary Research Opportunities in the Digital Age	33.183857
Awards and Conference closing	28.699552
Keynote - How to infuse AI into Business Processes - A practitioner's perspective on best practices	21.076233
Research Track Session 1 - Process Modeling and Conformance Checking (Triana Bridge)	19.730942
Research Track Session 4 - Modeling Support and Maintainability (Cathedral)	19.506726
AI4BPM - Morning Session	19.506726
Panel 1 - Publishing Culture in the BPM Community - Papers, papers, papers	17.937220
Presentation of Industry Forum and Demo Teasers	17.264574
Panel 2 - Privacy in Data-Driven Process Analysis - More Chance or Risk for Industry Adoption	15.470852

Table 9: Most attended sessions by academic participants

In the previous table, it can be appreciated that academic participants were tremendously interested in sessions about data mining and modeling. Alternatively, these are the least attended sessions by academic participants (table 10):

Session	BAP
Doctoral Consortium - Discussion and closure	3.139013
Workshop BPMS2'20	3.363229
Demos and Resources (Room 5)	3.363229
Demos and Resources (Room 4)	3.363229
Workshop SPBP'20	3.587444
Industry Forum Session 2	3.811659

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Session	BAP
Doctoral Consortium - Welcome and presentations by the PhD students	5.156951
Workshop DEC2H 2020	5.156951
Blockchain Forum Keynote	5.381166
Industry Forum Session 1	6.053812

Table 10: Least attended sessions by academic participants

Finally, it observes that academic participants were not interested in demos, workshops and forums. Another interesting aspect about the participants is the possibility of simultaneous attendance to different sessions. During the congress, there were sessions whose schedules coincided, so it was possible to attend to more than one session at the same time. We have checked if participants tried to take advantage of this success, by calculating the average of simultaneous attendance of all participants (table 11):

Simultaneity average	Participants
2.50	1
1.66	4
1.75	5
2.00	5
1.50	39
1.00	783

Table 11: Averages of simultaneous attendance

Where it can be concluded, that the vast majority of the participants has not attended simultaneously to more than one session in general, even though some participants have attended more than session in some cases, since their simultaneous attendance averages are bigger than one session but not greater than two sessions in general. Only a few participants have attended to two or more sessions in general, since their simultaneous attendance averages are

equal or bigger than two sessions at the same time.

Finally, we have clustered participants in groups depending on their attendance percentages to sessions, which has led us to these groups (figure 12):

Figure 12: Best clustering groups depending on the attendance percentages to sessions by participants

4. Analysis of participation in Other Sessions: Mindfulness, Social Events, Coffee with Authors and Sponsors Sessions

4.1. Mindfulness

There was a mindfulness session each day of the congress in the morning, therefore there were 5 mindfulness sessions that received a total of 200 participants and there was an average of 57.4 participants in the sessions. The number of participants who attended each session and the percentage of average attendance time is shown in Table 12.

Session	Participants	%Attendance
Mindfulness Session 14/09/2020 09:40-10:00	125	38.1
Mindfulness Session 14/09/2020 13:30-13:50	16	48.2
Mindfulness Session 15/09/2020 09:40-10:00	71	39.0
Mindfulness Session 16/09/2020 09:20-09:40	33	27.9
Mindfulness Session 17/09/2020 09:40-10:00	42	50.7

Table 12: Participation in the Mindfulness sessions

Furthermore, in the following figure, we can see the relationship between the participants and the percentage of time they have attended the sessions. We have represented the data from the 5 sessions in a single graph (Figure 13).

Figure 13: Percentage of average attendance time in Mindfulness Sessions

4.2. Social Events

There were two Socials Events sessions in the congress. A total of 173 participants attended them, and there was an average of 103 attendees between both sessions. The number of participants who attended each session and the percentage of average attendance time is shown in Table 13.

Session	Participants	%Attendance
The BPM throwback bar	118	53.65
BPM for future	89	32.85

Table 13: Participation in the Socials Events sessions

In Figure 14 we can see the relation between the participants and the percentage of time they have attended the sessions. The sessions duration time corresponds to 100%.

Figure 14: Percentage of average attendance time in Socials events

4.3. Coffee with Authors

The coffee with authors received 51 participants in total, and there was an average of 1.64 participants in the sessions. Those participants have spent 15 minutes in average in the sessions. The majority part of the sessions (26 sessions) received at least one participant. In addition, there was more than one author in each session in average.

Last but not least, it is also important to highlight that the most attended coffee was "Enhancing communication of complex services through process modelling".

4.4. Sponsors Sessions

Finally, during the sponsor sessions there were 74 participants which spent 16 minutes in average in the sessions. Moreover, the average number of participants in the sessions was 8.03. In addition, the most attended session was the second session of talk to the editor.

Appendix A.

Evolution of simultaneous participants in each session

Figure A.15: Evolution of simultaneous participants in Doctoral Consortium - Welcome and presentations by the PhD students

Figure A.16: Evolution of simultaneous participants in Morning Session

Figure A.18: Evolution of simultaneous participants in Workshop SPBP'20

Figure A.17: Evolution of simultaneous participants in Doctoral Consortium - Discussion and closure

References

- [1] P. Sprent, Fisher Exact Test, Springer Berlin Heidelberg, 2011, pp. 524–525. doi:10.1007/978-3-642-04898-2_253.